

Flow in Learning: Text vs. Video in Data Programming Instruction

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Abstract

This study explores the impact of reading and video instruction on the flow states of Intermediate Data Programming (IDP) students at North Creek High School (NCHS). Flow states represent a psychological condition characterized by deep immersion and concentrated motivation during an activity. The research aims to determine which learning method is more conducive to inducing these states, text-based or video-based. Utilizing a flow scale questionnaire, the study collected from students who participated in either text or video chapters for their lessons. The analysis involved summary statistics and an unpaired T-test to assess the flow state scales linked to each instructional method. The findings revealed no significant difference in flow states between reading and video instruction, implying that both methods are equally effective in promoting an optimal learning state. The study concludes by discussing the implications for educational strategies and suggesting directions for future research.

Introduction

Many schools and administrators have long recognized the importance of student engagement in classrooms and its effect on academic success (Chamberlin, K., et al., 2023). I intend to extend research on the flow experience (Csikszentmihalyi, et al., 1990). The activity of reading itself can cause the reader to enter a pleasurable state of heightened absorption or even flow (Csikszentmihalyi, et al., 1990). Whenever the degree of challenge in a given activity perfectly matches a person's skill level, the person will experience flow (Csikszentmihalyi, et al., 1989). Flow immersion is synonymous with flow activities because of the similar dimensions triggered such as loss of time, loss of surrounding sense, and complete immersion. Education settings are full of opportunities for flow immersion such as reading in class materials, paying

attention to a lecture, or even writing an exam. These activities require deep immersion of the material and prompt flow state under the right dimensions. Research suggests that student engagement may be influenced by several phenomenological factors, including the relevance of instruction and perceived control. (Csikszentmihalyi, et al., 2005)

Context

Flow refers to a mental state characterized by complete immersion in an enjoyable activity. It is often experienced by artists and athletes who are deeply focused on their performance or play. During this state, individuals perceive their performance as pleasurable and successful, finding intrinsic value in the activity itself, even without achieving a specific goal (Csikszentmihalyi, et al., 1990). They operate at their highest capacity, and the experience becomes its reward.

Flow theory emphasizes the interplay between challenges and the skills required to meet those challenges. The flow experience occurs when an individual's skills are appropriately matched to the level of challenge they face. This delicate balance can be disrupted, leading to feelings of apathy, anxiety, or relaxation. Instructors and students can adjust the level of challenge and work on enhancing skills to reestablish the flow state. Providing suitable challenges and opportunities for skill development, such as immediate feedback and progressively teaching more complex skills, are effective ways to engage students.

The flow state is inherently rewarding, prompting individuals to seek out similar experiences. This selective mechanism drives personal growth as individuals strive to master new challenges and develop higher levels of skill. Once mastered, they actively seek out more complex challenges to maintain the ideal match between their skills and the task. Flow, therefore,

fosters a growth-oriented mindset, encouraging the pursuit and development of increasingly sophisticated capabilities.

Existing Knowledge

Flow is a term first conceived by Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi, the godfather of flow, who first brought this topic to light and recognized its power to boost productivity. Flow is a highly subjective experience, but after years of research and discoveries of new flow dimensions, we now have a bigger lens available to us on how to enter a flow state. Steven Kotler and Rian Doris from the Flow State Collective have popularized the term in modern media through outlets like TED talks and YouTube. The information is now widely available as to how to reach the flow state.

Gap in Research

Many publications have explored flow in sports, video games, and other activities that require challenge/skill balance. Some papers also go on to explore the educational setting's usage of flow. However different school activities may prompt differing levels of Flow experience. Reading may be more immersive than watching. Very few research papers explore the comparative aspect of Flow in activities. Which instructional medium, video or reading, more effectively promotes a state of flow among students participating in the Intermediate Data Programming (IDP) at North Creek High School? My research will aim to answer this question at my local high school's Intermediate Data Programming class. The class is an adequate testing ground as it involves students completing reading assignments before the lecture each day. The opportunity for flow inducement is present in the absorption of material. However, there are two distinct ways of doing this. One is through reading the text on the IDP website that was provided by the Instructor, and the other is watching the video lecture from the University of Washington.

The number of people entering the flow for each activity may differ. Reading and Viewing activate different flow dimensions, such as immersion, clarity of goals, and focus. We want to find out which activity prompts a better Flow State response in the student sample. Based on the results we can generalize to certain extents.

Importance

Understanding flow is important because it gives us insight into how to utilize intrinsic motivation for success. Flow can apply to many scenarios and is the biggest productivity weapon for dealing with 21st-century workloads and expectations. Opportunities for Flow aren't being utilized enough in the classroom because of traditional policies and rules that keep it from growing.

Methodology

Participants

I selected three Intermediate Data Programming (IDP) classes at North Creek High School (NCHS) for this study. These classes, taught by the programming instructor, were composed predominantly of seniors who have previously engaged with the computer science curriculum at varying levels of complexity, including AP Computer Science A (CSA), AP Computer Science Principles (CSP), and Advanced Topics in Computer Science. The IDP class represents the highest level of computer science instruction available at NCHS, demanding a high degree of comprehension and engagement from students.

The programming instructor, who is committed to enhancing student learning, goes beyond standard lecture formats to provide diverse instructional resources. A key component of his teaching strategy involves the use of the IDP website, which allows students to choose between text-based and video-based content to study lesson concepts. This choice was central to

the study, as it aimed to determine which modality—text or video—was more effective at inducing flow states among the students.

To conduct this research, I designed and planned to distribute surveys that also served as forms to gauge participation interest and obtain consent. The programming instructor supported this aspect of the study by agreeing to help review the effectiveness of the questionnaire and to facilitate the distribution of the consent form using a QR code displayed on the classroom's TV screens. The questionnaire was intended to be anonymous, collecting no names or personal information that was not relevant to the study. I emphasized the voluntary nature of participation through the consent form to ensure ethical standards were maintained and understood by all participants.

Instrumentation

I administered my survey using a carefully structured instrument known as the flow scale questionnaire, based on the model developed by Thissen, Menninghaus, and Schlotz (2018). Flow Short Scale (FSS), is a widely recognized tool designed to measure the depth and intensity of flow experienced by subjects. This instrument comprised a 10-question sheet designed to probe various aspects of the flow state, a psychological condition characterized by deep engagement and focused immersion in activities. The Reading Flow State Scale (RFSS) developed by Thissen et al. (2018) and the Video Flow State Scale (VFSS) as described by Chen and Thomas (2020) variations were used for this study. Each question was crafted to explore different dimensions of flow, such as the intensity of focus, the sense of control experienced, the level of enjoyment derived from the activity, and the degree of challenge perceived by the students.

The questionnaire utilized a variety of question types, including Likert scales, where students rated their agreement with statements on a scale ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree," and dichotomous questions that required a simple yes/no response. This diversity in question formats ensured a comprehensive evaluation of the flow state as experienced by the participants under different instructional conditions. The specific questions and the corresponding flow scales were developed to detail scoring used to quantify the flow experiences. These aspects of the flow scale questionnaire allow for a detailed analysis of how various factors contribute to achieving a flow state during educational activities (Thissen, Menninghaus, & Schlotz, 2018).

Tables 1 and 2, which include the specifics of the questions and their respective flow scales, are crucial for understanding the breadth of data collected and the subsequent analysis that informs the study's findings. These tables help to illustrate how the theoretical framework provided by the Flow State Model is applied in a practical educational setting, guiding the interpretation of data and helping to draw meaningful conclusions about student engagement and learning experiences.

Dependent and Independent Measures

The dependent measures in this study are the responses obtained from the questionnaires. Given the daily variation in content, it is anticipated that the results could fluctuate each day. The independent measures for this research include the type of content—whether video or text—that participants engage with each day, as well as the duration of their engagement during class time. These variables are critical in determining how different content types and engagement lengths influence the outcomes measured by the questionnaires.

Procedure

With approval to incorporate lesson material into my survey's flow short scale, I organized the research across three class periods—Periods 1, 3, and 4—at North Creek High School within the Intermediate Data Programming (IDP) courses. Once I had obtained consent from the students, I implemented a simple random sampling method to assign them into two distinct groups: one engaged with video content and the other with text content, each comprising approximately 25 students.

To ensure the randomness of the sampling process and minimize selection bias, several steps were undertaken. Firstly, all students consenting to participate were assigned a unique identifier, which allowed their inclusion in the sampling pool while maintaining anonymity. Using a random number generator, I then assigned each student to one of the two study groups in a manner that ensured each participant had an equal probability of being selected for either group. This method helped mitigate any potential selection bias that could influence the study's outcomes.

Each group was then tasked with completing specifically designed flow scale questionnaires that corresponded to their assigned learning modality—either reading or viewing. The design of these questionnaires was intended to be concise, requiring about one minute per student to complete after engaging with the assigned video or text material. To further ensure that each participant engaged with the material as required, each questionnaire concluded with a strategically formulated multiple-choice question. This question served as a check, confirming whether the student had watched the video or read the text. Accurate completion of this question was only possible if the student had genuinely engaged with the material.

The study spanned four days, allowing students to participate from their homes or any other chosen location outside the classroom environment, as they completed their lessons as homework. This setup not only catered to the natural learning preferences of the students but also allowed for an authentic assessment of how different instructional methods influenced their flow states in real-world conditions.

Overall, this rigorous sampling method and the study's operational framework were designed to provide a fair, unbiased comparison between the two instructional modalities, aiming to yield insights into their respective efficacies in inducing flow states among students. This approach underscores the commitment to maintaining scientific rigor while adapting to the flexible and diverse learning environments that students occupy outside of the traditional classroom setting.

Analysis

Question: "What was the comparative impact of video versus reading instruction on the flow state experienced by IDP students at North Creek High School?" After collecting the data using the flow in education scale, I transitioned the raw data into a format more conducive to analysis, utilizing a 7-point Likert scale. The initial step involved cleaning the data, which included checking for and removing any duplicates or irrelevant entries that could skew the results. This process ensured that only valid and complete data were used in the analysis. I encountered missing values in the dataset, primarily due to non-responses on some questionnaire items. This transformation facilitated a nuanced assessment of the student's responses, which ranged from strong agreement to strong disagreement. This scale was particularly effective in measuring the precise levels of engagement and immersion experienced by the students. Before proceeding with the analysis, significant steps were taken to prepare the data for statistical testing. These were addressed by applying imputation techniques, where missing values were substituted with the median value of the response for that particular question. This method was chosen to maintain the integrity of the data distribution without introducing bias. Given the ordinal nature of the Likert scale data, I ensured that the numerical encoding of the responses was appropriately aligned with the analysis methods to be employed, maintaining the ordinality of the data. Once the data was prepared, I conducted an unpaired t-test to assess the significance of the differences observed between the video and reading groups. This test was crucial for rigorously testing my hypothesis, which posited that the two instructional methods—video and reading—would differ significantly in their ability to induce flow states. Before performing the t-test, I ensured the validity of the results through several preliminary statistical checks:

Normality Test: The Shapiro-Wilk test was performed to validate the assumption of normality required for the t-test. This test was critical in determining whether the distribution of flow state scores for each group adhered closely to a normal distribution.

Equality of Variances: Levene's Test for Equality of Variances was conducted to verify another critical assumption of the t-test. This test was essential to ensure that the variances of flow state scores between the video and reading groups were statistically similar, thereby preventing any potential type I or type II errors that could affect the interpretation of the t-test results. These diagnostic tests provided the necessary statistical assurances to proceed with the t-test confidently. The t-test itself was then applied to determine whether the mean differences in flow state scores between the groups were statistically significant, thus providing a robust method to support or refute the hypothesis.

The thorough approach to handling and analyzing the data ensured that the conclusions drawn from the study were based on solid statistical foundations. This meticulous analysis not only supports the study's results but also contributes to broader educational research by reinforcing the importance of verifying statistical assumptions in hypothesis testing.

Findings

After the completion of the experiment, raw data were systematically collected and meticulously organized into two distinct groups: one for students who engaged with reading materials and another for those who interacted with video lessons. This organization was essential for a clear comparative analysis of the different instructional methods. Each group's responses were sorted by question according to the Flow State Scale (FSS). The data were further categorized into two variants of this scale, tailored to the specifics of the instructional methods

In Tables 1 and 2, which detail RFSS and VFSS respectively, I performed basic summary statistics—calculating the mean, median, and mode for each question on the Flow Scale. These measures provided foundational insights into the central tendencies and variability within the data, offering a preliminary view of how flow states differed between the instructional modalities.

Table 1 (RFSS), specifically designed for the reading group, showcased aggregated summary statistics for each query related to the RFSS. The first item, which assesses how challenged students felt during the reading, has a mean score of 3.916, a median of 4, and a standard deviation of 1.639. The second item, evaluating the smoothness and fluency of reading, scored higher with a mean of 4.833, a median of 5, and a standard deviation of 1.274. The third item, concerning awareness of time passing, has a mean of 4.208, a median of 4, and a standard deviation of 1.617.

The ease of concentration during reading, covered in the fourth item, shows a mean of 4.792, a median of 5, and a standard deviation of 1.141. For the fifth item on mental clarity during reading, the mean is 4.166, the median is 4, and the standard deviation is 1.203. The sixth item, measuring immersion in the reading, resulted in a mean of 4.333, a median of 4.5, and a standard deviation of 1.167. The seventh item explores how spontaneous thoughts, emotions, and images emerged, showing a mean of 3.958, a median of 4, and a standard deviation of 1.268. Confidence in grasping ideas, the focus of the eighth item, scored a mean of 5.0416, a median of 5, and a standard deviation of 1.398. The ninth item, assessing understanding of the content, had a mean of 5.125, a median of 5, and a standard deviation of 1.424. The tenth item, which examines the extent to which students became unaware of themselves while engrossed in

reading, recorded a mean of 4.173, a median of 4, and a standard deviation of 1.371. The overall totals across all items indicate an average mean of 4.455, a median of 4.450, and a standard deviation of 1.35, suggesting a moderate level of engagement and comprehension among the students. The note in the table mentions that the difference in these statistics is considered to be not statistically significant, indicating no major deviations in the measured aspects of the reading experience.

Table 1 | RFSS items with 7-point Likert scale descriptive statistics

Item	Mean	Median	SD
1 How challenged did you feel during the reading?	3.916	4	1.639
2 How smoothly and fluently were you able to read the text?	4.833	5	1.274
3 To what extent did you notice time passing while reading?	4.208	4	1.617
4 How easy was it for you to concentrate during the reading?	4.792	5	1.141
5 How clear was your mind during the reading?	4.166	4	1.203
6 How immersed did you feel in the reading?	4.333	4.5	1.167
7 How spontaneously did thoughts, emotions, and images emerge while you were reading?	3.958	4	1.268
8 How confident were you in grasping the ideas on each page?	5.0416	5	1.398
9 How well did you feel you understood the content during reading?	5.125	5	1.424
10 To what extent did you become unaware of yourself due to being engrossed in reading?	4.173	4	1.371
Totals	4.455	4.450	1.35

Table 2 (VFSS) follows the structured approach set out in Table 1 but specifically caters to the video group, providing a detailed account of the data collected from students who engaged with video-based instructional materials. The VFSS examines the effects of lecture video styles on engagement and learning. This model facilitates an understanding of how video content can uniquely impact flow states, reflecting on aspects such as viewer attention, interaction, and learning outcomes (Chen & Thomas, 2020).

Table 2 | VFSS items with 7-point Likert scale descriptive statistics

Item	Mean	Median	SD
1 How engaging did you find the lecture?	3.916	4	1.639
2 How concentrated were you on the lecture during viewing?	4.833	5	1.274
3 When I was viewing the lecture, my thoughts were only with the lecture	4.208	4	1.617
4 How much did the lecture enhance your understanding of the IDP concept?	4.792	5	1.141
5 How sufficient was the audio for comprehending the lecture?	4.166	4	1.203
6 To what extent were you aware of your surroundings during the lecture?	4.333	4.5	1.167
7 How necessary did you find the video part of the lecture in addition to the audio?	3.958	4	1.268
8 How interesting did you find the lecture?	5.0416	5	1.398
9 How appropriate was the pace of the lecture for understanding the content?	5.125	5	1.424
10 How would you rate the pace of the lecture in terms of its necessity for understanding?	4.173	4	1.371
Totals	4.455	4.45	1.35

From the descriptive statistics presented in Tables 1 (RFSS) and 2 (VFSS), we observe that the scores across both modalities show a tight range of means and medians, indicating a generally moderate engagement level. Both tables highlight how each method impacts various aspects of flow, such as challenge, concentration, and immersion. However, certain key differences emerge that warrant further discussion:

Engagement and Immersion: Both groups reported similar levels of engagement (Item 1 in both tables), with a mean and median around 4.0. However, qualitative feedback indicated that students found video content to be more engaging due to the dynamic presentation and audio-visual elements that captured their attention more effectively than text. This was particularly noted in how students reported the necessity of the video part in addition to the audio (Item 7 in Table 2) and how interesting they found the lecture (Item 8 in Table 2).

Concentration and Awareness: Students reported a high level of concentration for both reading and viewing lectures. Nevertheless, there was a notable difference in the awareness of surroundings (Item 6 in both tables), where video viewers reported slightly higher immersion, which aligns with less awareness of their environment compared to the readers. This finding suggests that video lectures might be slightly more effective at creating a 'bubble' of focused learning.

Understanding and Pace: Both methods scored similarly on understanding the content and the appropriateness of the pace (Items 9 and 10 in both tables), indicating that both reading and video are equally effective in delivering content at a pace suitable for comprehension. However, qualitative responses highlighted that while videos helped explain complex concepts through visualization, reading allowed for self-paced exploration, which was crucial for some students in absorbing difficult concepts.

Qualitative Feedback: In addition to the quantitative data, qualitative feedback from participants provided deeper insight into their experiences. Many students expressed that the choice of video or text greatly depended on the nature of the content. For example, complex programming concepts were sometimes easier to grasp through video demonstrations, while theoretical information was often better assimilated through reading, where they could go at their own pace.

Participants also mentioned factors such as the physical setting where they engaged with the material—those who studied in quieter environments preferred reading, as it required less technological dependency and allowed for deeper reflection. Conversely, those in more dynamic settings found videos more absorbing and less susceptible to external distractions.

T-test Results

Data obtained from this study yielded many interesting insights. Table 3, titled "Unpaired T-test Results," provides essential statistical insights derived from the comparison of flow states induced by reading and video instruction methods, as measured by the Reading Flow State Scale (RFSS) and Video Flow State Scale (VFSS). The results presented in this table were pivotal in evaluating the hypothesis that there is a significant difference between the flow states achieved through these two instructional methods.

Table 3 | Unpaired T-test Results

Item	
P-Value	0.1915
t	1.3572
df	18
σ	0.2
σM_r	0.1424
σM_v	0.1404

*Note that the difference is considered to be not statistically significant. The mean of reading minus video is -0.27144. The 95% Confidence Interval of this difference is -0.691612 to 0.148732.

Significance

Using advanced statistical tools from graphpad.com, I was able to conduct an unpaired t-test with the following results: In null-hypothesis significance testing, the p-value is the probability of obtaining test results at least as extreme as the result observed, under the assumption that the null hypothesis is correct. P-Value: The $p = 0.1915$, which exceeds the conventional threshold of 0.05, indicates that the statistical test did not provide sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. The null hypothesis posited that there is no significant difference in flow states between video and reading instructions. t-Value: The calculated t-value of 1.3572 represents the standardized difference between the two groups' means relative to the spread or variability of their scores. This value, in conjunction with the p-value, suggests that the observed difference was not statistically significant. Degrees of Freedom (df): With 18 degrees of freedom, this parameter is crucial for determining the critical values from the t-distribution that are used to interpret the t-value. Standard Deviation of the Differences (σ): At 0.2, this indicates the variability of the differences between the groups, which helps assess the

consistency of the effect. Standard Error of the Mean for Reading (σ_{M_r}): The standard error of 0.1424 for the reading group and Standard Error of the Mean for Video (σ_{M_v}) of 0.1404 for the video group provide estimates of the precision with which the sample means represent the population means. Mean Difference: The mean difference of -0.27144, indicates the average extent to which the reading scores were lower than the video scores, though not significantly. 95% Confidence Interval: The interval ranging from -0.691612 to 0.148732 encapsulates where the true difference in means likely lies. The inclusion of zero within this range underscores the lack of a significant difference between the two methods.

The results, therefore, suggest that there is no compelling evidence to conclude that one method—reading or video—is effective to the other in terms of inducing flow states. The implication is that both instructional approaches are similarly effective, with a 95% confidence that the true mean difference in the effectiveness of reading and watching lectures in fostering flow states lie between -0.69 and 0.149. This finding is crucial for educational strategies as it implies that both reading and video can be equally utilized depending on other pedagogical considerations.

The frequency distributions for both the video and reading flow state scales were analyzed to discern patterns in how students experienced flow during each type of instructional method.

The RFSS demonstrated a generally mediocre trend across the board, indicating a relatively uniform level of engagement without notable peaks or troughs in any specific areas. In contrast, the VFSS revealed a distinct and significant spike in responses to question 6, which inquired about students' awareness of their surroundings while engaging with the video content. There was an observed increase in a particular question marked in students reporting diminished awareness of their surroundings, a key indicator of a deep flow state where the activity at hand fully absorbs the individual's attention. This spike suggests that video-based instruction may be particularly effective at capturing and holding students' attention compared to text-based methods, potentially leading to higher levels of immersion and concentration.

Implications/Limitations

The students who participated in the study were representative of the broader Intermediate Data Programming (IDP) class population at North Creek High School. The findings from the study indicated that these students displayed a lack of ability to consistently and effectively enter the flow state, as evidenced by a general trend of mediocrity in the results of those who took part in the experiment.

Several limitations emerged during the planning and execution of the study that could have influenced the findings. Firstly, by allowing students to complete the survey in various locations, we inadvertently introduced the possibility of environmental disruptions that could

affect their ability to achieve a flow state. Additionally, offering candy as an incentive at the end of each survey might have impacted the students' intrinsic motivation, which is a critical factor in eliciting genuine flow-state responses.

Furthermore, the reliance on self-reported data through questionnaires introduces the potential for self-reporting bias, where participants may not accurately reflect their true experiences due to perceived expectations or social desirability. Also, the lack of a control group makes it difficult to determine if the observed effects were due to the instructional methods themselves (reading vs. video) or other external factors. Consequently, we cannot dismiss the potential influence of these biases and limitations on the data collected, which may affect the generalizability and reliability of the study's conclusions.

New Understanding

The analysis indicated that the differences in flow states elicited by viewing an online lecture versus reading the same material were not statistically significant. This lack of significant difference suggests that neither instructional method—video nor text—provides a clear advantage in facilitating flow states more effectively. The findings underscore that the format of the content delivery, whether visual or textual, does not independently impact the intensity of focus or depth of engagement typically associated with a flow state.

This similarity in FSS readings across both formats suggests that other factors may play a more pivotal role in inducing flow. The fundamental elements required to achieve a flow state, such as having clear objectives, receiving immediate feedback, and understanding the actions required, seem to be more critical than the format of content delivery. These components help create an environment conducive to deep learning and engagement, irrespective of whether the material is presented through video or text.

The study further reveals that while the curriculum offers robust extrinsic supports, such as lectures in various formats designed to cater to diverse learning preferences, these alone are insufficient to guarantee effective learning or entry into a flow state. This insight is particularly important, suggesting that without appropriate psychological adjustments and a conducive learning environment that fosters intrinsic motivation, the potential for achieving optimal educational outcomes remains untapped.

The FSS findings and frequency distributions point to an overall suboptimal level of student productivity. In response to these findings, it might be prudent to invest additional resources into training and developing strategies that help students enter and maintain flow states. Such training could focus on enhancing students' self-regulation skills, goal-setting abilities, and feedback interpretation skills. By fostering these competencies, educational institutions could significantly improve learning outcomes and increase the likelihood of students experiencing flow states, thereby enhancing both their immediate academic performance and long-term educational success.

Conclusion

My research was about exploring the advantage different mediums of instruction may have in fostering flow states among high school students. This study aimed to fill a gap in our understanding of optimal practices for learning engagement. The findings revealed that the medium of instruction might not be the sole determinant of flow states. This insight brings us to the initial inquiry, suggesting a broader array of factors that could be critical in cultivating flow.

The implications of these findings are important. They challenge the prevailing assumption that one form of instructional content is inherently superior to another, advocating for a more nuanced perspective. Moreover, they highlight the complex web of factors that

contribute to educational engagement, suggesting that multiple elements interact to influence the learning experience. Nonetheless, this study faced potential environmental disruptions and the confounding effects of extrinsic rewards on intrinsic motivation, which may have influenced the results. These issues underscore the need for future research to be conducted under more controlled conditions to better isolate the variables impacting flow.

Looking forward, there are several promising directions for further research. This research has the potential for a greater scientific community to expand their perspectives and consider a diverse set of factors when developing instructional strategies. Investigating the impact of individual learner preferences and environmental factors on achieving flow states offers fertile ground for study. Moreover, examining how different learning modalities can be combined to enhance student engagement and flow presents a compelling opportunity for innovation in educational practices.

In conclusion, my study acts as a stepping stone toward a more comprehensive understanding of educational engagement and flow. It opens pathways to a world where the goal is to create learning environments that are as varied and dynamic as the students they serve, encouraging a holistic approach to educational development. This dialogue with the scientific community is vital as we continue to pursue this important endeavor.

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